

Infographics: Tool for Enhancing The Level of Knowledge in Contextualized Filipino Literature of Grade 11 Students

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to determine the effectiveness of infographics in enhancing the level of knowledge in contextualized Filipino literature among Grade 11 students. This study employed a quasi-experimental design. The researcher selected two groups from Grade 11 Filipino students in a high school, serving as the control group and the experimental group. A questionnaire was used as the instrument, which underwent validity and reliability testing. Statistical tools such as frequency and percentage, paired sample t-test, and correlation analysis were used to obtain research findings.

Based on the results, it was found that the outcomes of the control and experimental groups differed in the initial assessment. The control group had excellent results, with a mean of 26.10, contrasting with the experimental group, which had a mean of 11.04, indicating the lowest performance. Consequently, the researcher decided to utilize infographics to enhance the level of knowledge in contextualized Filipino literature, and the experimental group demonstrated their proficiency in Filipino literature, with a total mean of 32.90 points, indicating excellent performance in the final assessment. Using paired sample t-test, the researcher discovered that the experimental group significantly improved and increased their scores in the final assessment. This study also revealed the effectiveness of using infographics in enhancing the learning level in Filipino literature and creating a Simplified Teaching Guide for Teaching Filipino Literature.

Based on the study's findings, the Department of Education (DepEd), particularly Jasaan National High School, is encouraged to provide rigorous training on how to utilize infographics in Teaching Contextualized Filipino Literature.

Key Words: Infographics, Medium, Contextualized Filipino Literature, Visual Learning

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is an art because it is a work that requires resourceful use of knowledge and skills to achieve the desired result. This is a helping hand in the greatest work of charity. The teacher gives and the students receive knowledge, wisdom and guidance not in a forced way. He teaches them how to understand, appreciate, decide and judge the truth. He encourages those who are taught to answer freely and think about how a Filipino teacher is expected to possess the skill and ability to lead his students to a successful decision.

According to Garcia (2012), infographics are a useful learning tool for students of all ages to organize, clarify, and simplify complex information—they help students develop of understanding by exploring relationships between concepts. Teacher-generated infographics are a useful scaffold to support student learning. Students today learn better when they see, hear and feel something, especially in the classroom.

According to Enriquez (2016), infographics help make students' learning more beautiful and clear and facilitate their learning. With the rapid changes caused by modern technology, teachers will have the knowledge and technological skills to adapt to the digital age. In the field

of education in the modern era there are individuals who possess the skill and ability to teach using information in technological communication or Information and Communication Technology (ICT).

It was said in the study of Carlos (2018) that infographics can help to visualize and develop ideas, organize and/or order information, plan what to write, increase reading comprehension, brainstorming, organize problems and solutions, compare and contrast ideas, show cause and effect, and more. In addition to being effective for teaching vocabulary, graphic organizers can also enhance reading comprehension by helping students categorize information and show relationships between important concepts.

Modern teaching and technological changes in the 21st century are the focus of competition in schools today. Modern teaching is fully aware of the benefits to students and teachers. Concepts are more expanded because students can see more what the specific subject wants to convey. But according to Novak (2016), the traditional teaching method focuses on the teacher as a controller of the students' environment. The teacher is responsible for what method to use with the student.

Pursuant to DepEd Order no. 31 s. of 2012, Policy and guidelines on the implementation of Grade 1 to 10 and the K to 12 basic education curriculum. One of the subjects taught by the Department of Education for students to study is the Filipino subject titled "Reading and Analyzing Various Texts for Research" for students in the 11th grade. Senior High School in all STRANDs in the second semester of the school year. Students in the 11th grade of Senior High School are having difficulty in learning and understanding some of the Filipino literature. The decrease in their scores in their performance task and written task is an indication that some of the competencies have not been cultivated and this has become a problem facing the researcher today.

During the three years of the researcher's teaching, he saw that not all learning skills were learned by the students, especially in Filipino Literature. Because of this problem, the researcher thought to address the problem through Infographics as a medium to develop the level of learning in contextualized Filipino literature. The infographic will serve as a research intervention. Infographics are an effective tool to use in the classroom. When applied to content areas, infographics enhance learning and understanding of difficult concepts and ideas. Using infographics in the classroom helps make content accessible to all levels of students. In addition to being effective for teaching vocabulary, graphic organizers can also enhance reading comprehension by helping students categorize information and show relationships between important concepts.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a quasi-experimental design that according to the research of Thyer (2012), it is similar to the use of preliminary and final exams in two groups of respondents. The only difference is that the second group of respondents will be given a different task after checking the accuracy of the result. From here there is one (1) section of baiting-11 (Faithful), the control section and the experimental section (Humility) used in the study design.

It used a purposive sampling or intentional study method in obtaining respondents. The respondents in this study are the students from grade-11 which of the three sections only two (2) sections will be used as respondents. The results of the test or evaluation of the students in the 11th grade in the school where weaknesses were found in the learning of the subjects contained in Filipino 11 should also be the basis. It is good to use the deliberate selection of the respondents because it is expected the researcher will handle the teaching of their subject and carry out the planned intervention.

The following statistics will be the basis of this research in order to solve the problems faced by the researcher. Problems 1 and 2 used the mean, frequency and standard deviation to

determine the level of learning to read contextualized Filipino literature of the control and experimental groups in the initial estimation. In Problems 3 and 4, T-test for paired samples was used to find out if there is a significant difference in the learning level of the control and experimental groups after the final prediction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Learning Level of the Control and Experimental Groups in the Pre-Test

The research in Table 1 shows the learning level of the control and experimental group based on their pre-test. Below is the result of the assessment of the teaching of contextualized Filipino literature before the application of infographics as an intervention.

Table 1: Learning level of the control and experimental groups in the pre-test

Points	Control			Experimental		
	Frequency	%		Frequency	%	
32-35	9	18		0	0	
28-31	19	37		0	0	
25-27	19	37		0	0	
21-24	4	8		6	12	
0-15	0	0		45	88	
Total	51	100		51	100	
Mean	26	Std. Deviation: 4.48	Average quality	Mean:11	Std. Deviation: 3.64	Did not meet expectations

In the conducted forecast, the researcher noticed that the result in the first forecast of the two groups was different with an overall mean of 26.10 in the control group which means average performance, and 11.04 mean in the experimental group which means that it did not meet expectations. The result data indicate that the experimental group needs to be intervened by the teacher in order to change their performance and make their learning meaningful.

According to DepEd Order 23 s. 2015 that average-ability students strive to demonstrate an accurate broad and deep understanding of the subject matter through any three of the six aspects of understanding- explanation, interpretation, application, insight , empathy and self-awareness or any other indicator of understanding, where the connection to a wide range of contexts and the use of perspectives and reflections is evident and the students who do not meet the expectations cannot demonstrate an accurate broad and deep understanding of the subject through any three of the six aspects of understanding- explanation, interpretation, application, insight, empathy and self-knowledge or any other indicator of understanding, where the connection to a wide range of contexts and the use of perspectives and reflections is evident.

Level of Learning of the Control and Experimental Groups at the Post-Test

In the description, it can be seen that the control and experimental group improved their ability to understand what they read using infographics. It can be observed that the experimental group got a mean score of 32.90 which means very good, while the control group has a mean score of 29.76 which means good.

Table 2: Level of learning of the control and experimental groups at the post-test

Points	Control			Experimental		
	Frequency	%		Frequency	%	
32-35	23	45		41	80	
28-31	22	43		9	18	
25-27	6	12		1	2	
21-24	0	0		0	0	
0-15	0	0		0	0	
Total	51	100		51	100	
Mean	30	Std. deviation 3.26	Good	33	Std. deviation 3.50	Very good

Table 2 shows the final estimates of the two groups. The control group scored a mean of 30 which means good and the experimental group scored a mean of 33 which means very good. It shows that the score of the students in the experimental group improved.

According to Garcia (2017), students have a greater chance of learning their lesson when pictures are applied or videos are watched, especially with reading materials such as poetry, short stories and others. Also in Carlos 2015 stating that students learn better when they see something in their studies such as pictures, videos and other teaching aids. In accordance with Deped order no. 78 series of 2012 states that "DCP aims to provide public schools with appropriate technologies that would enhance the teaching-learning process and meet the challenges of the 21st century."

Bernales (2015) said, there is a great opportunity for a person to learn when things are seen, heard, touched and felt. It is stated that there is a greater chance that students will learn more in learning Filipino literature by applying infographics and that infographics can also help teachers in teaching Filipino literature to facilitate the learning process of students more - especially in the teaching of Filipino literature

Difference in Learning Outcomes of the Control and Experimental Groups at the Pre-Test and Post-Test

In Table 3 can be seen the result of the control and experimental group in the Introduction and t final forecast.

Table 3: Difference in Learning Outcomes of the Control and Experimental Groups at the Pre-test and Post-test

Group	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Experimental	11.04	3.64	Did not meet expectations	32.90	3.26	Very good
Control	26.10	4.48	Good	29.76	3.50	Good

The researcher noticed that there was a difference in the result of the initial prediction between the experimental and control group. It can be seen in the table that the experimental group has a mean of 11.04 and a standard deviation of 3.64 which indicates that it did not reach and it is opposite to the result of the control group

According to Howard Gardner in his theory of multiple intelligences, each person has different ways of learning things. In the study of Nuna (2016), the teacher should consider the style and teaching tools that will be used in the students' learning of the subject.

Difference in the Post test Result of the Control and Experimental Group

In Table 4 it can be seen that there is a significant difference between the results of the experimental and control groups. It can be seen with -4.79 t-value and 0.00 p-value with interpretation significant. This means that infographics as a medium for teaching Filipino literature is an effective teaching tool that teachers can use to facilitate the learning process of students.

Table 4: Difference in the post-test result of the control and experimental group

Post- Test Result						
	Mean	SD	t	t_c	P-value	Interpretation
Control	29.76	3.50	-4.97	1.68	0.00	Significant
Experimental	32.90	3.26				
*Significance at $p \leq 0.05$						

Thus, the first initial hypothesis that says "there is no significant difference in the learning outcomes of the control and experimental groups after the final assessment," was not rejected. The results of this research showed that students learn Filipino literature better when it is used as a teaching method or intervention infographics.

The results showed that the experimental group that used infographics as a teaching tool showed a higher score compared to the control group. It says that the use of infographics in case studies is a very effective tool in teaching Filipino Literature.

Strengths and Weaknesses of Students' Infographics in Promoting the Learning of Contextualized Filipino Literature

Table 5 shows the strengths and weaknesses of the students who used the intervention in learning Filipino literature. By conducting a focus group discussion (FGD) the most common answers of the respondents were gathered.

Table 5: Strengths and weaknesses of students' Infographics in promoting the learning of contextualized Filipino literature

Strengths	Number	Percent age	Weaknesses	Number	Percent age
The students get a lot of points	5	10	It takes a long time to finish answering because the infographics used are being reviewed or looked at again.	31	55
It is good to use infographics in teaching Filipino literature because the flow of the story or any form of literature is better understood.	26	50	Sometimes it takes a long time because not all students are given the answers right away, so they will be given enough time to understand and answer each question.	20	45
Infographics are easy to use in teaching literature because they are not just text.	10	20			

Not only was the infographic pasted on the blackboard, it could also be seen on the TV that our teacher used.					
The topic is easy to understand because of Beautiful and colorful infographics Many are attracted to creativity and everyone listens to the discussion. Infographics are one of the best IMs because they are clear, colorful, illustrated and not boring to look at in the discussion.	10	20			
Total	51	100		51	100

According to five (5) students with ten (10) percent, the score they got in the forecast increased significantly and increased because of the infographics. It is good to use infographics in teaching Filipino literature because the flow of the story or any form of literature is better understood according to 26 students. Some students said that infographics are easy to use in teaching literature because they are not just text. The infographics are not only pasted on the blackboard but can also be seen on the TV used by our teacher and the subject is easy to understand because of the beautiful and colorful infographics. Many are attracted to creativity and everyone listens to the discussion. Infographics are one of the best IMs because they are clear, colorful, illustrated and not boring to look at in the discussion.

As a weakness, some of the students said that it took a long time to finish answering because they were going back or looking again at the infographics that were used. Sometimes it takes a long time because not all students are given the answers right away, so they will be given enough time to understand and answer each question. Therefore, it would be good to use infographics in the teaching of Filipino literature only because students need enough time to answer each question.

Alkhezi and Ammar (2015) emphasize that students should be given enough time to answer the questions on the forecasts to be carried out especially in the literature.

Table 5 shows the equipment that will be developed based on the results of the study. Through this research, a "Simplified Teaching Guide for Teaching Filipino Literature" will be developed that includes various topics and infographics that can be used in Teaching.

Infographics on Teaching Contextualized Filipino Literature

Table 6 shows the infographics on Teaching Contextualized Filipino Literature where there are topics reserved for each infographic to be used.

Table 6: Infographics on Teaching Contextualized Filipino Literature

Subject Matter	Objectives	Flow of the discussion	Resources	Time Frame
Lesson 1: Analysis of short and artistic poetry	Different elements, techniques, and literary devices are identified in poetry	The teacher will start the discussion by asking questions that can give an idea of the topic to be discussed.	Questionnaires <i>HELE Infographics</i>	

<p>"A MOTHER'S HELE TO HER FIRST-BORN"</p> <p>Poetry from Uganda</p>	<p>Certain poetic forms and conventions are identified</p> <p>Uses selected poetic elements in short writing exercises</p> <p>Discovering new techniques in writing poetry</p> <p>Can write poetry using different elements, techniques, and literary devices</p>	<p>The teacher will discuss about a contextualized literary work which is the poem titled "Hele ng Ina Sa sang panganay."</p> <p>In the discussion of this topic infographics will be applied that will respond to the students' learning.</p> <p>After the discussion, the teacher will give a Task that can be found in the module on the topic discussed.</p> <p>The tasks : Group work Short Quiz</p>	<p>Series of pictures</p> <p>Teacher's Manual</p> <p>Teacher's guide</p> <p>Module/ Textbook</p>	<p>Week 1</p>
<p>Lesson 2:</p> <p>Text analysis of short paragraphs or vignettes that use diction, image building, bridges and specific experiences</p> <p>SHORT STORY</p> <p>"The story of an hour"</p> <p>Written by Kate Chopin</p>	<p>The objectives:</p> <p>Identify the difference between poetic writing and other forms of writing</p> <p>Relates ideas from experiences*</p> <p>Language is used to elicit emotional and intellectual responses from the reader</p> <p>Uses imagery, diction, bridges, and specific experiences</p>	<p>The discussion will be started by the teacher giving questions or motivations that can give an idea of the topic to be discussed.</p> <p>The teacher will discuss a contextualized literary work which is a short story titled "The story of an hour."</p> <p>In the discussion of this topic infographics will be applied that will respond to the students' learning.</p> <p>After the discussion, the teacher will give a Task that can be found in the module on the topic discussed.</p> <p>The tasks : Group work Short Quiz</p>	<p>Questionnaires</p> <p>Time Flow infographics</p> <p>Series of pictures</p> <p>Teacher's Manual</p> <p>Teacher's guide</p> <p>Module/ Textbook</p>	<p>Week 2</p>
<p>Lesson 3:</p> <p>Analysis of a feature scene/scene in a short story</p>	<p>Identify various elements, techniques, and literary devices short story (fiction)</p> <p>Identify different styles of short story (fiction) construction</p>	<p>The teacher will start the discussion by asking questions that can give an idea of the topic to be discussed.</p>	<p>Questionnaires</p> <p>HangPa Infographics</p>	<p>Week 3</p>

<p>Based on the Departure (Summary) Translated by Juliet U. Rivera</p>		<p>The teacher will discuss about a contextualized literary work titled “Hango sa Paglisan (Summary) Translated by Juliet U. Rivera”</p> <p>In the discussion of this topic infographics will be applied that will respond to the students' learning.</p> <p>After the discussion, the teacher will give a Task that can be found in the module on the topic discussed.</p>	<p>Series of pictures</p> <p>Teacher’s Manual</p> <p>Teacher’s guide</p> <p>Module/ Textbook</p> <p>Instructional equipment</p>	
<p>Lesson 4:</p> <p>Analysis of a feature scene/scene in a short story</p> <p>“ Love Lost and Found at the Berlin Wall”</p>	<p>Able to write a journal and some short exercises that use the basic elements of a short story (fiction)*</p> <p>Writing a short scene using</p> <p>Answers questions</p>	<p>The discussion will begin by giving questions or motivations that can give an idea of the topic to be discussed.</p> <p>The teacher will discuss a contextualized literary work which is a short story titled</p> <p>“Love Lost and Found at the Berlin Wall”</p> <p>In the discussion of this topic infographics will be applied that will respond to the students' learning.</p> <p>After the discussion, the teacher will give a Task that can be found in the module on the topic discussed.</p>	<p>Questionnaire</p> <p>Love infographics</p> <p>Series of pictures</p> <p>Teacher’s Manual</p> <p>Teacher’s guide</p> <p>Module/ Textbook</p>	<p>Week 4</p>
<p>Lesson 5:</p> <p>Analysis of short and artistic poetry</p> <p>"Love"</p>	<p>Different elements, techniques, and literary devices are identified in poetry</p> <p>Certain poetic forms and conventions are identified</p>	<p>The teacher will start the discussion by asking questions that can give an idea of the topic to be discussed.</p> <p>The teacher will discuss about a contextualized literary work which is the poem titled “Ang Pag-ibig.”</p>	<p>Questionnaire</p> <p>Love Infographics</p> <p>Series of pictures</p> <p>Teacher’s Manual</p>	<p>Week 5</p>

		<p>In the discussion of this topic infographics will be applied that will respond to the students' learning.</p> <p>After the discussion, the teacher will give a Task that can be found in the module on the topic discussed.</p> <p>The tasks : Group work Short Quiz</p>	<p>Teacher's guide</p> <p>Module/ Textbook</p>	
<p>Lesson 6:</p> <p>Text analysis of short paragraphs or vignettes that use diction, image building, bridges and specific experiences</p> <p>Based on the Departure (Summary) Translated by Juliet U. Rivera</p>	<p>Objectives: Relates ideas from experiences* Language is used to elicit emotional and intellectual responses from the reader Uses image formation, diction, bridges</p>	<p>The discussion will begin by giving questions or motivations that can give an idea of the topic to be discussed.</p> <p>The teacher will discuss a contextualized literary work which is a story titled- Hango sa Paglisan (Summary) Translated by Juliet U. Rivera</p> <p>In the discussion of this topic infographics will be applied that will respond to the students' learning.</p> <p>After the discussion, the teacher will give a Task that can be found in the module on the topic discussed.</p> <p>The tasks : Group work Short Quiz</p>	<p>Questionnaire</p> <p>HangPa Infographics</p> <p>Series of pictures</p> <p>Teacher's Manual</p> <p>Teacher's guide</p> <p>Module/ Textbook</p>	<p>Week 6</p>
<p>Lesson 7:</p> <p>Analysis of a feature scene/scene in a short story</p>	<p>Objectives</p> <p>Identify different styles of short story (fiction) construction</p>	<p>The discussion will begin by giving questions or motivations that can give an idea of the topic to be discussed.</p> <p>The teacher will discuss a contextualized literary work that is a short story.</p> <p>In the discussion of the topic, it will be applied with infographics that will respond to the students' learning.</p>	<p>Questionnaire</p> <p>Series of pictures</p> <p>Teacher's Manual</p> <p>Teacher's guide</p> <p>Module/ Textbook</p>	<p>Week 7</p>

This table shows the topics that infographics will be applied to in Teaching Filipino literature. However, each topic has a dedicated infographic. Infographics are visual presentations of information that use design elements to represent content. Infographics have been used throughout history to convey complex ideas to audiences in a way that facilitates awareness and understanding. The images seen are taken from Region 4A-Calabarzon, Philippines.

According to Carlos 2017, infographics are an effective tool to more easily teach literature to students. Not all infographics are suitable for the topic to be discussed so it is appropriate to analyze and understand the infographic carefully if it is suitable for the topic to be taught.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the outcome of the study, the following was known: It was discovered that infographics best supported the development of students' learning level in contextualized Filipino literature. In this research, it was found that students in grade 11 in Filipino in a high school show improvement in the level of learning of Filipino literature after applying an intervention in the use of infographics. As a final note, the difference between the experimental group showed that their final estimate increased and broadened their knowledge in learning Filipino literature. The strengths and weaknesses of using infographics in learning Filipino literature are also laid out.

The theory of constructivism has proven that the use of teaching tools that have calmed the changing or current reality of life. Sentapi (2012) said, the theory of Constructivism is to keep pace with the changing world, and it seems to be a spiral that starts from the past towards the present. This will give the students an interesting and unique experience using modern teaching tools. According to Howard Gardner's Multiple Intelligences Theory, which focuses on Visual-Spatial learning, students have different ways of learning things, one of which is visual learning.

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